

Global Branding: Issues and Challenges

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Abstract

With the rapid pace of globalization the time has forced the marketers to consider global branding. Around two decades ago, Theodore Levitt (Harvard Business School professor) clearly stated in his article, “The Globalization of Markets,” that a worldwide market for homogeneous products and services had evolved. Marketers interpreted from his article that global need to homogenize products, packaging, and communication to attain a least-common-denominator positioning that would be effective across cultures. During 1980s this thought proved popular, when several countries opened up to foreign competition as well as some American and Japanese corporations tried to penetrate those markets with international brands and marketing programs. Simultaneously, global branding required specific attention as the world economy constantly kept on integrating.

As a result of this revolution in marketing and branding the global managers have gone to craft mix strategies. They attempted for worldwide actions in different areas like technology, production, and organization while specific product features, communications, distribution, and selling practices were tailored to local consumer requirements. These “glocal” strategies have played dominant role in marketing ever since. However it is difficult for the global brands to escape notice, in the minds of consumers global brands have never been more prominent, whereas most of global corporations have not realized outlook of people for them is different than they have for other firms. Since their commonness and pervasiveness, global brands are seen as dominant and powerful organizations that are capable of doing great things.

The research has (involving 3,300 consumers in 41 countries), found that due to differences in the brands’ global qualities most people prefer one global brand over another. The firms must learn to manage distinctiveness and features rather than overlooking the global characteristics of their brands. This is more significant because the prospective growth for most companies is likely to come from foreign markets. In 2002, developed countries in North America, Europe, and East Asia accounted for 15% of the world’s population of 6.3 billion.

The purpose of this paper is to bring out understanding of global branding, trace the significance of global branding, to discuss challenges and issues pertaining to global branding. This paper also cites various examples of MNCs that reached the worldwide markets through global branding.

Keywords:

Global Branding, Multinational Corporations (MNCs), Globalization

1. Introduction

The global brand is defined as the brand that has a widespread regional/global awareness, availability, recognition and demand. Moreover, global brand has same name with consistent positioning, messages, personality, look, and feel across major markets, marketed by centrally coordinated marketing strategies and programs. Levitt's (1983), motioned in his one of the article on globalization of markets, several advantages associated with moving towards global brands have been identified. From a supply side perspective, global brands can create economies of scale and scope in R&D, manufacturing, sourcing, and marketing. According to Neff (1999), global brands can be launched faster in foreign markets as it takes is relatively less time-consuming for local modifications. Global brands are benefited from their unique image worldwide because of consistent positioning. Hassan and Katsanis (1994) opined that such a global positioning increases the strategic appeal of a brand as consumers around the world develop similar needs and tastes.

In marketing literature the term "global brand" has been defined in a different way. Two different schools of thought have defined it differently. The first school has defined it based on the marketing standardization literature. According to this school the primary motivation of companies for building global brands is to benefit from strong economies of scale and scope. Craig and Douglas (2000) supported that a standardized brand can create significant cost savings in marketing, R&D, sourcing, and manufacturing. Hassan and Katsanis (1991) expressed, by focusing on such a global appeal the cultural, structural and regional differences can be addressed easily, and the global brand will benefit from a unique perceived image in all of its markets, especially when targeting global consumer segments, such as the affluent and the teenagers. Studies on standardization have defined global brands as brands that use similar brand names, positioning strategies, and marketing mixes in most of their target markets. Nevertheless, even within this stream, there is no agreement as to how standardized global brands are. For example, Levitt (1983) focused on the complete standardization of the brand's strategy and marketing mix elements when defining a global brand, whereas the majority of the studies contend that complete standardization is unthinkable and brands differ in their degree of globalization. Aaker and Joachimstaler (1999)

found, some brands are more global than others with respect to differing levels of achieved standardization. Later, the second school of thought defined the term 'global brand' from the consumer perceptions perspective. Steenkamp et. al. (2003), cited that a global brand is defined as the extent to which the brand is perceived to be global and marketed not only locally but also in some foreign markets. This definition implies that as the perceived multi-market reach of a brand increases, the Perceived Brand Globalness (PBG) increases as well.

The globalization of markets has put global brands in the center stage. The evidence is everywhere; on the streets, in stores, in the media all around us. Global brands are exerting their power and influence within various domains. In economic terms, the high price premiums they command are met with negligible resistance on the part of consumers. In the psychological domain, global brands are perceived as creating an identity, a sense of achievement and identification for consumers, symbolizing the aspired values of global consumer culture. Through the process of meaning transfer consumers transfer these values and ideals to their self-concept (McCracken, 1986).

Multinational corporations (MNCs) are not indifferent to the importance of global brands. In fact, many of the strategic actions of MNCs are fueling the growth of global brands. In the last decade, many multinational corporations have pruned their brand portfolios in favor of global brands (Schuiling and Kapferer, 2004). For example, since its Path to Growth strategy was launched in 2000, Unilever has reduced the number of brands in its portfolio from 1600 to 400 leading brands and under 250 tail brands (www.unilever.com). This enables Unilever to concentrate resources on a portfolio of leading global brands with strong growth potential that best meet the needs and aspirations of people around the world. Around the same time, P&G also pruned its brand portfolio in favor of global brands (Pitcher, 1999). Similarly, Colgate Palmolive has invested a lot in making Colgate Total a global brand name just as Frito-Lay has done with its Lay's brand. These and many other companies are betting their futures on global brands.

Kapferer (2005) argues that the global brand of the past which was ideally standardized in most respects of its marketing has been replaced by the post-global brand - the brand that approaches standardization at the regional level rather than at

the global level. The current literature, unfortunately, offers only a limited insight into what a global brand means, how the globalness of the brand can be measured, what are the drivers of attitudes toward global brands, and why and when are consumers more likely to purchase global brands. Ambiguous and confusing definitions of global brands exist which discourage robust measurement models from developing furthermore, while the topic is of interest to diverse research streams ranging from global consumer culture to signaling theory in information economics, each research stream approaches global brands in isolation and from a different perspective.

1.1 Significance of Global Branding

With the above discussed theories in mind, in recent times, researchers have tried to answer the following question: What makes global brands significant? Some studies examined the impact and importance of perceived brand globalness (PBG) on attitude and purchase likelihood (Steenkamp, Batra and Alden 2003; Batra et al. 2000; Tasoluk 2006). The main logic is that PBG creates consumer perceptions of brand superiority and thus preference for global brands even when quality and value are not ‘objectively’ superior (e.g., Kapferer 1997; Keller 1998; Shocker, Srivastava, and Ruekert 1994). A study including consumers from the US and South Korea found PBG to be positively related to both perceived brand quality and prestige and through them to purchase likelihood (Steenkamp, Batra and Alden 2003). In a developing country setting, Batra et al. (2000) found a direct relationship between the perceived non-localness of the brand and attitude towards the brand, where non-localness was measured by perceptions of multi-market reach. In a recent study, Tasoluk (2006) did not find a significant relationship between PBG and brand purchase likelihood. In the same line of reasoning, in a large scale study covering 1800 respondents in 12 countries Holt, Quelch and Taylor (2004) found that the global myth elicited from global brands was found to explain on average 12% of the variation in brand preferences worldwide.

Drawing upon consumer culture theory, the authors view global brands as one of the key symbols of shared conversation where global brands help “create an imagined global identity that they share with like-minded people (p.71) and thus have a global myth dimension. With regard to perceived quality, Steenkamp, Batra and Alden (2003) and Holt, Quelch and Taylor (2004) found quality to have a significant direct association to global brand preference. In Holt, Quelch, and Taylor’s (2004) study, quality signal explained on average 44% of brand preferences. Prestige is another construct identified in the literature as driving global brand preference. Steenkamp, Batra and Alden (2003) found that brand

globalness significantly increased purchase intent through perceived prestige. In another study, Batra et al. (2000) found that brands perceived as non-local were attitudinally preferred to brands perceived as local in an emerging market setting (i.e. India). Although not tested empirically, the authors attribute this positive relationship to status enhancement motivations in addition to perception of high quality of non-local brands. Social responsibility is another important association that consumers use in making choices among global brands (Holt, Quelch and Taylor 2004; Tasoluk 2006). By social responsibility, consumers expect global brands to act in a socially responsible way while conducting their businesses. It should be noted that perceived brand social responsibility is a criterion used only when consumers are evaluating global brands but not when evaluating local brands. In fact, social responsibility explained on average eight percent of global brand preferences. While empirical papers on global branding are scant, this embryonic stream of research has identified perceived brand globalness (global myth), quality, prestige and social responsibility as important associations of global brand preference.

As the economic clout of global brands increased, research firms have also tackled the definition and identification issues. Practitioner-oriented studies such as those by ACNielsen and Business Week/Interbrand use objective measures including the actual multi-market reach of the brand, percent of sales coming from outside the domestic market, and minimum revenue generated globally to qualify for being a global brand. According to ACNielsen (2001), “global brands are those which are present in the four major regions of the world – North America, Latin America, Europe / Middle East, East Africa, Asia – with at least 5% of sales coming from outside the home region, and total revenues of at least \$ 1 bn.” Based on these criteria, 43 brands were qualified as global in 2001. The economic clout of global brands is demonstrated by the fact that the top three of the brands in this list commanded a sales value of greater than 100 billion dollars in 2001. Similarly, each year Business Week together with Interbrand develops a list of the world’s most valuable brands (i.e., The Top 100 Brands). The criteria used in identifying the brands are the following: About a third of sales of each brand must be generated outside of its home country; the brand must have awareness outside of its base of customers; and, the brand must have publicly available marketing and financial data (Business Week 2007). Furthermore, Business Week/Interbrand rankings consider market leadership, stability, and global reach – the ability to cross both geographical and cultural borders – in calculating brand strength.

1.2 Challenges and Issues Pertaining to Global Branding

With entry in the new millennium, marketers are in an era of unprecedented paradox. Society is reacting to the uncertainty that comes from unprecedented change, with a desire to return to simpler times and values, and this has a direct impact on brands¹. This might be called as the yin and yang of the late 20th Century: technology and humanism side by side. Brands that are both symbolic of sweeping change (Intel, Microsoft), as well as brands that reflect timeless, simple (read that simpler) values (Coca-Cola, Levis), Brands that are stuck in the middle will likely whither and die.

The 21st century brought lots of challenges for marketers for their brands. There have been many changes like, an unparalleled rate of change, driven to a large degree by technology. The underlying need for all multinational marketers is to cope with such change, and to understand how it impacts consumers, and ultimately their relationship with brands. Therefore, using global brands pose great challenges and opportunities.

Marketers face various challenges while establishing the global brand. To create and establish the global brands different issues at the organizational level need to be addressed.

Fundamentally, there are two strategic parameters affecting decisions on global branding. They are:

1. The relative strength of globalization pressure in that particular industry, and
2. The degree to which the company has internationally transferable assets.

If globalization pressures are weak and the company's assets are (including the brand) are not transferable, then the company need not go in for a global brand. It should concentrate on creating a higher brand value in the domestic market. If globalization pressures are strong and the company has transferable assets, then it should look at extending these to a similar market using a global brand.

2. Creating Captivating Brand Associations

The first and foremost challenge that needs to be taken into consideration when creating a global brand is the name and the related word-mark, or symbol, that will be used to represent the company, product, or service throughout the world. The name must be pronounceable in all languages and dialects, free of negative connotations, and not confusingly similar to existing names. This is not so difficult for most corporate brand names, such as McDonald's², Ford³, or Visa⁴, but finding a multi-lingual product or service brand name that stands out from the crowd and works with equal success in all countries and cultures is a much trickier proposition. Sometimes, it is a case of linguistic embarrassment, such as the translation of Pepsi's Come Alive with the Pepsi Generation, which in Chinese translated into Pepsi Brings Your Ancestors Back from the Dead.

Other times, it is a matter of cultural context, such as the use of the word *diet* in the Diet Coke brand name, which has either no relevance or an undesirable connotation in several countries and so necessitated the use of Coca-Cola Light as an alternate name. The challenge was to create a compelling branding system that would be consistently recognizable in 146 world markets, whether named Diet Coke or Coca-Cola Light. Coca-Cola positioned its product as a soft drink that would help people look and feel their best rather than one solely centered around the notion of losing weight. In this way, they hoped, consumers would perceive these characteristics just by looking at the product's graphics, regardless of the name it bore. The resulting combination of unique brand visual equities and clear expression of product attributes not only transcends name difference but can also be easily identified whether that name is rendered in English, Korean, Chinese, or Cyrillic⁵ characters.

As it can be seen from the Diet Coke example, trade dress has to remain as consistent as possible in order to create a strong brand expression across all markets, particularly with the emergence of satellite television, the Internet, and an ever increasing amount of air travel. Ultimately, if consumers cannot recognize "their" brands in advertising or on the shelf, they may decide to switch to competitive brands. In principle, brand identity and distinct positioning messages are best communicated across all countries through packaging graphics that are as standardized as reasonably possible. That said, changing the name slightly for different markets around the world is not as negative as one might think. People tend to recognize brands first by their signature color schemes and unique graphic elements and second by their names.

3. Country Association: A Dilemma

Some global brands are strongly associated with their country of origin. Indeed, in certain categories this is part of the essence of the brand. Automobiles are the most obvious example. The German cultural psyche is embodied in Mercedes-Benz⁶, Porsche⁷, and BMW⁸—and what is more Italian than a Ferrari? Other categories are actually defined by their region of origin: Dom Perignon Champagne¹⁰, Jack Daniels whiskey¹¹, and Jose Cuervo Tequila¹² could not exist as such if they did not evoke specific areas within France, Tennessee, and Mexico. Still other famous brands are deeply rooted in the folklore of their birthplace, such as Levi's California Gold Rush heritage or Harley-Davidson's association with American "outlaw" imagery—a symbol of freedom. The strength of these associations can be remarkably potent in the international marketplace. It is up to companies either to emphasize these associations to their advantage or to recognize that their path to brand success is to be found by trying to embody the world's cultural differences into their brand. This has proved successful for companies like Yahoo, whose Web sites, derived from the American model, are country-specific. While always maintaining its slightly "on the edge" brand personality and never taking itself too seriously, Yahoo subtly modifies both content and communications for each of its 23 country-specific sites. Remaining consistent across all sites, and therefore linking each country to the brand, are color usage, typography, brandmark, and other graphic devices. Each country name is tightly linked to the brand by incorporating it into the logotype. However, the sites appear in the local language (or dialect) of each country, and content—from news to interest groups to banner advertising—is tailored accordingly.

4. Different Context and Cultural Differences

Beyond the product or service itself, the visual identity of the brand also faces problems of acceptance. A color or a design that achieves a positive result in one country may not have the same effect in another. Although the package or logo must portray the product's or company's values, attributes, personality, and positioning, it must also ensure that cultural

tastes and differences are taken into account. In other words, a global brand must retain its autonomy while also adhering to local sensitivities. Starbucks recently encountered loud protests when it signed a year's lease to operate a store within the Forbidden City, in Beijing, China. The coffee retailer boldly erected its trademark green-white-and-black sign, as it had done in hundreds of other locations around the world, and was immediately branded as a capitalist invader of this sacred place, despite the fact that there are many other non-Chinese shops and restaurants within the same walls. The cries to have Starbucks thrown out died down when the company adopted a more discreet signage program. Starbucks' mistake lay in not understanding that its proud display of brand could also be seen as a brash intrusion into a cultural shrine. An example of a more positive approach in China relates to Pepsi, the number-one soft drink in China. Although its on-pack graphics, recognizable anywhere in the world, were not significantly altered for the Chinese market, the brand has been extremely successful in portraying a local image and establishing an emotional bond with Chinese consumers. One way this was achieved was by effectively using brand promotion specifically tailored for the Chinese audience. While Britney Spears for Pepsi and Christina Aguilera for Coke are fighting it out on the front lines of the "cola war" in the United States, Faye Wong, a very popular Chinese pop star, is persuasively endorsing Pepsi to her throngs of Chinese fans, making it "their" brand.

5. Issues related to Physical Packaging

An often-overlooked, or at least underestimated, component of a brand's personality is the physical packaging itself. The distinctive shape of a package can become so recognizable that it often becomes the cornerstone of a brand's advertising, as exemplified by the long-running Absolut¹³ campaign that has successfully positioned its unique bottle profile as a central theme in print ads around the world. Shape equity is one of the more difficult assets to acquire, especially on a global basis, but once established it can be a powerful visual mnemonic. The trademark contour bottle created for Coca-Cola in 1915 to fend off copycat products has become so ubiquitous that a simple outline drawing of the bottle would be instantly recognized anywhere in the world. That said, it would be wrong to think that a physical shape on its own would afford a product the global status of Coca-Cola and Absolut. Many years of cultivating consumer relationships and building their brand reputations have given them the stature they have today. For example, the little blue box that has become the global signature of Tiffany & Co¹⁴ is not solely used to communicate the company name but is also a way of symbolizing the quality and craftsmanship of its products.

6. Societal Pressures and Environmental Effects

Public pressure can heavily influence the types of products that are marketed and how they are made and packaged. Greenpeace is a particularly powerful social and political force internationally, influencing companies to actively pursue more environmentally friendly processes and procedures. More and more companies are designing and producing packaging and labels with nontoxic, soy-based inks; nonpolluting solvents; recycled and recyclable materials; redeemable glass, aluminum, and plastic containers; less material waste; and so on. This can present a challenge to the execution of a unified global brand strategy, since production and printing capabilities, as well as environmental consciousness, can vary considerably in different parts of the world. Environmental issues do not just stop at packaging. Consumers are also becoming more aware of how their products are obtained, grown, and produced. Many of these issues will be responded to differently, often quite vehemently, in different regions around the globe. For example, whale products are sold in Japan as almost a matter of national pride, whereas in the US, a can of tuna will not be purchased unless the package displays a seal assuring that dolphin-friendly fishing techniques were employed. A more recent hot topic has been the use of genetically modified organism (GMO) vegetable and grain crops; the use of GMO grain, whether intentional or inadvertent, in everything from corn chips to baby food has spurred massive product recalls. Once again, prominent on-pack assurance that a given product uses only non-GMO grain has become an important part of package communications in some categories. Indeed, many consumers now consider the brand behind the brand; it is no longer the product that has to consider environmental issues but also the entity as a whole. To their customers, employees, franchisees, stakeholders, and suppliers, The Body Shop is seen as more than a manufacturer of skin and hair care products—it is an entity committed to animal and environmental protection and to human rights. For example, its Web site discusses environmental and social issues, as well as marketing Body Shop products. Social pressure can also have a serious impact on the graphic design or trade dress of a product. Even a best-selling brand with many years of built-up brand equity can now be deemed offensive. When the Colgate-Palmolive Company acquired a 50 percent share of Hong Kong's Hawley & Hazel Company in order to build production capacity in Asia, it soon found it had also acquired 100 percent of a controversy precipitated by one of Hawley & Hazel's brands—Darkie toothpaste. Although never considered racially offensive

in Asian markets, where the name had little, if any, literal meaning, civil rights pressure in the United States quickly made it clear that Colgate-Palmolive's partial ownership of this brand in its current state would not be tolerated. The problem to be solved was compounded by the fact that the brand represented significant market share throughout Asia and that any changes to the brand's graphics had to maintain recognizable visual equities. Colgate-Palmolive set about removing this perceived example of racial stereotyping by adopting the name Darlie¹⁵, with the same letter count and general appearance as the word Darkie. And instead of featuring a drawing of a black minstrel, the packaging now sports a portrait of a man of ambiguous race wearing a silk top-hat, tuxedo, and bowtie.

7. Diversity in Legal Aspects

Marketers will also find that governmental control in matters of package labeling can differ greatly from country to country. In the United States, for instance, much of the copy on package labels—in particular, product descriptions, net weight statements, and health or nutritional claims—is tightly regulated by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). The exact wording, and even the size and formatting of the type to be used for much of this information, is spelled out by the Nutrition Labeling and Education Act 1994 (NLEA). To complicate this situation further, if the product contains meat, it has to adhere to additional on-pack requirements via the US Department of Agriculture (USDA). Yet another set of rules applies if a product contains enough alcohol to fall into the realm of the Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco and Firearms. And, of course, any regulation that dictates the way in which a great deal of the copy on a package must be displayed will necessitate the modification of any other text and images, if they are to fit on the package. Other countries have package-copy guidelines that are either much more lenient or very different from those in the US, and this creates an obvious hurdle for consistent global communication. Although some degree of multinational uniformity is achieved because of commerce within the European Union or as a result of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), language differences are still very much a factor. Marketers hoping to do business in Canada have struggled for years to meet the English-French dual-language requirements, especially in Montréal and the eastern provinces. True multi-language packaging is even more complicated if a company attempts to satisfy all language and regulatory requirements within one universal package. This usually works more successfully with nonfood products that have fewer regulations to deal with in the first place. Tax legislation can open a Pandora's box of a different sort, one that surprisingly can even affect the kind of

graphics or visual images a product's package can display. In Argentina, for instance, tax laws are quite stringent in regard to reproduction of fine artwork on commercial packaging. If a company wants to use a well known painting or illustration as part of its package, it must either alter the artwork enough to qualify it as "original," as Coca-Cola had to do when they used vintage Haddon Sundblom Santa¹⁶ illustrations (as shown in the picture) on their Christmas packaging, or be prepared to pay a significant tax penalty.

There is so much to contemplate when creating a branding strategy for the global marketplace that the list of factors to consider sometimes seems unwieldy. The positives and negatives of creating one global brand versus localized adaptations, or remaining associated with the country of origin versus embodying cultural differences, must be weighed against each other. However, despite these complications, great global brands tap into basic human needs and aspirations. There can be no stronger global brand platform than one that speaks directly to customers and improves their lives—no matter how small or incremental that improvement.

8. Conclusion

To market brands worldwide and to market worldwide brands are not the same thing. For a brand to be global or worldwide it must by definition have commonly understood set of characteristics and benefits in all of the markets where it is marketed. Abilities of brands to create consistency in maintaining similar perceptions across countries and cultures determine whether a global brand is a practical solution or not.

An effective strategy is to adopt brand standardization. Though brand standardization is a common strategy, marketers tend to build a global brand by adopting local practices e.g. using local language in advertisements. However, each strategy has its own merits and usefulness. Moreover, dropping a weak brand and consolidating multiple brands under one brand name proves a wise strategy. While a global brand across the countries provides cost savings by eliminating duplication of design and artwork, production, distribution and communications issues, it is also loaded with pitfalls unless well planned and executed.

The relative strength of globalization pressure in that particular industry and the degree to which the company has internationally transferable assets determine whether go for global brand or not. People tend to recognize brands first by their signature color schemes and unique graphic elements and second by their names. The strength of country association can be remarkably potent in international marketplace. A global brand must retain its autonomy while also adhering to local sensitivities. The distinctive shape of a package can

become so recognizable that it often becomes the cornerstone of a brand's advertising. Social and environmental pressure can have serious impact on design of packaging, labels, graphic design of a product. Governmental control in matters of package labeling can differ from country to country.

An international brand name should avoid negative connotation, should reflect the desired product image (related with particular country), possibly be unique and distinctive and should indicate or suggest "globalness". Strategy of pronouncing or spelling a brand name in a foreign language may influence product perceptions and attitudes. Brand name can be made more international by paying special attention to its *pronunciation*. With respect to legal aspects of branding a name that is similar to other firms' trademarks should be avoided. Once selected the brand name must be protected through registration and other measures should be taken to prevent any infringement of that name.

9. EndNote

1 By Howard J., Dir., Global Brand Marketing, the Coca-Cola Co., PO Drawer 1734, Atlanta, GA 30301, in his article on, *The challenges of global marketing in the next millennium*, retrieved from <http://ift.confex.com/ift/98annual/techprogram/accepted/26-6.htm>, retrieved on December 21, 2008.

2 McDonald's Corporation is the world's largest chain of fast food restaurants, serving nearly 47 million customers daily. It is a recognized global brand in the fast food business.

3 The Ford Motor Company and a global corporate brand is an American multinational corporation and the world's fourth largest automaker based on worldwide vehicle sales, following Toyota, General Motors, and Volkswagen.

4 Visa Inc., commonly referred to as VISA, is a multinational corporation based in San Francisco, California, USA. The company operates the world's largest retail electronic payment network, managing payments among financial institutions, merchants, consumers, businesses and government entities

5 It is derived from Greek alphabet.

6 Mercedes-Benz automobiles are available at dealerships in more than 129 countries and their work fleet (trucks and commercial) vehicles are available from a group of dealers worldwide as well as direct from the factory. Mercedes-Benz has a full range of passenger, light commercial and heavy commercial equipment. Production is on a Global basis.

7 Porsche SE or Porsche is a German manufacturer of automobiles, which is majority-owned by the Porsche and

Piëch families. Porsche SE holds two chief assets, the first of which is Dr. Ing. h.c. F. Porsche AG, often shortened to Porsche AG, manufacturer of the Porsche automobile line.

8 BMW is a worldwide manufacturer of high-performance automobiles and motorcycles, and is the current parent company of both the MINI and Rolls-Royce car brands.

Ferrari S.p.A. is an Italian sports car manufacturer based in Maranello, Italy. Founded by Enzo Ferrari in 1928 as Scuderia Ferrari, the company sponsored drivers and manufactured race cars before moving into production of street-legal vehicles in 1947 as Ferrari S.p.A.. Throughout its history, the company has been noted for its continued participation in racing, especially in Formula One, where it has enjoyed great success.

9 A region of northeastern France, moreover, it is a white sparkling wine either produced in Champagne or resembling that produced there.

11 A liquor made from fermented mash of grain.

12 Mexican liquor made from fermented juices of an Agave plant.

13 ABSOLUT VODKA is one of the world's best selling premium spirits brands and achieved sales of 10.7 million nine-liter cases in 2007 (96.6 millions of liters). Some 500,000 bottles of ABSOLUT VODKA are produced every day. Every bottle of ABSOLUT VODKA is produced in Åhus, in southern Sweden.

14 Tiffany & Co. is a U.S. jewelry and silverware company founded by Charles Lewis Tiffany and Teddy Young in New York City in 1837 as a "stationery and fancy goods emporium." As part of its branding, the company is strongly associated with its Tiffany Blue color, which is a registered trademark.

15 IT is an Offensive term for Black people.

16 Haddon Hubbard "Sunny" Sundblom was a United States artist best known for the images of Santa Claus he created for The Coca-Cola Company. Sundblom is best remembered for his advertising work, specifically the Santa Claus advertisements he painted for The Coca-Cola Company in the 1930s.

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